

Current payment systems utilized by Small, Medium and Enterprises (SMEs) in Botswana

by

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1.0 Abstract

Digital Payment platform has been used in Botswana since 2006. This paper examines the current digital payment systems used in Botswana and their adoption by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Secondary published data is applied in the paper to explore the impact path analysis of the relevant construct to establish the relationship between payment systems and adoption by SMEs. Online published data from 2006, when the first digital payment system in Botswana, known as Botswana Interbank Settlement System (BISS) in 2006 was adopted to the current payment system as per-2025 are used is utilized.

The findings highlight that the current digital platforms identified in Botswana include internal settlements such as interbank settlements, intrabank settlements and mobile money payment systems. The international payment systems, rarely used by SMEs, are SWIFT and PayPal. Further, it was found that minimum payment systems significantly impact the payment of low-cost transactions by SMEs. The significant association of digital payments and efficiency is also partially mediated by payment policy. The main implication of the study is that SMEs are not financially inclusive, and the majority have failed to adopt digital payment systems in preference for cash payments. Therefore, policymakers can use the findings to develop unified payment system policies for low-transaction payments. This study is unique as no other study has been conducted on the linkage of payment systems used in Botswana and the efficient use by SMEs. There are financial exclusion risk implications for SMEs management, opportunities for the government and the financial system of Botswana to improve the policy and incorporate a lower denominations payment system for SMEs to be included.

Keywords: *BISS, BoB, UPI, Open-API and SMEs.*

1. Introduction

The major role of the modern payment systems in Botswana is to facilitate funds transfer/ payments between businesses, individuals and institutions to enable economic activities and financial stability of a country (Leslie, 2024). The financial payment system provides transactions for making and receiving payments using instruments such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM) cards, mobile money payments, Visa cards, electronic funds transfer (EFT) and cash (Fatonah *et al.*, 2018). Botswana's first digital payment was in 2006, known as the Botswana Interbank Settlement System (BISS) (Svotwa, Makanyeza and Weath, 2023). The objective was to reduce cash handling costs and improve efficiency in processing time and transparency. The growth of financial innovation in Botswana is to facilitate digital payments faster, more conveniently and with traceable transactions for businesses and individuals.

This paper evaluates the current payment systems used by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in conducting their businesses in Botswana. The purpose is to investigate the adaptability of the current payment systems by SMEs and individuals in making large and low-denominations transactions. The study separates SMEs in Botswana from large corporations in that many SMEs have lower denomination payments. This contrast large organizations that transact mainly in large denominations. The development of digital systems in Botswana favours large transaction volumes as compared to lower volume transactions, and SMEs are excluded. SMEs in Botswana perceive the high cost of transactions using modern digital technology. This brings a problem in the modern utilization of digital transactions by SMEs in Botswana.

The study problem statement emanates from the partial adoption of modern digital payment methods by SMEs in Botswana. Whereas digital transaction usage indicates a phenomenal growth rate of 98% across businesses in Botswana, Monye and Monye (2022) observe that 86% of SMEs have not adopted the use of digital services for their transactions. The general population are transiting into a cashless society with wide payment options for both small, medium and large businesses. Jeleka (2023) argues that the present high security risk is associated with holding cash for transactions. Kubanji *et al.* (2024) note that in 2024, Botswana Police statistics recorded 23% of cash theft in Botswana, with 70% of cash transactions coming from the business. This presents an increasing criminality in holding cash for transactions among the business sector. In addition to

this, security measures for small businesses poses large risk compared to large businesses with more advanced cash security systems in their businesses (King, 2018). For example, cash for large businesses is kept in a safe and collected by security companies. This contrast most of the SMEs who keeps cash in cash trays and collect the cash for deposit mostly by the entrepreneur (Monye and Monye, 2022).

The SMEs exclusion is also from the global transaction payment systems (Jeleka, 2023). There are several transaction systems in the world that originated in the United States of America (USA). Global real time payment systems include Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication (SWIFT) for international payments, bank transfers and the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), which connects the Real Time Gross Settlements (RTGS), which are rarely utilized by SMEs. This system operates 24 hours on a global payment system (Moravec, 2023).

However, Monye and Monye (2022) posit that despite their benefits, the majority of small businesses in Africa are not connected to global trade. Kganyame (2020) argues that most businesses in Botswana trade internally in cash, and mostly, the global payment systems are not convenient for small-value transactions. This lack of shift towards real-time payments reflects a narrow trend of digital age adoption. It demonstrates how African countries lag in utilizing a more efficient, quicker and better-aligned transaction system for business needs.

The papers seek to address the following objectives;

Objective 1: To identify payment systems by SMEs in Botswana

Objective 2: To propose a conceptual framework that guides the payment system for smaller denominations/ transactions.

Objective 3: To recommend how SMEs can be integrated into smaller denomination payments for their business transactions.

The significance of the study is its contribution to the development of a unified payment system model that integrates small and large denominations. The majority of SMEs highly depend on small denomination payment from a large customer base. The study contributes to suggestions on the best possible methods within the regulatory system of Botswana for integrating smaller

denominations for transactions. SMEs in Botswana depend on large volumes of smaller items they sell for profits. However, lower denominations are not accommodated by the commercial banking system, mobile money services and other digital banking systems in Botswana. The findings contribute to the literature review on payment systems by SMEs, specifically in Botswana. The choice of financial inclusion for SMEs and regulatory loopholes that could facilitate SMEs' financial inclusion and lower denomination into the current payment system are also highlighted.

2. Literature review

Forger and Julie (2020) state that the role of the modern technological payment system is to facilitate payment across all business levels with ease of doing business and speed. Moravec (2023) contends that technological payment systems offer speed, improve financial inclusion, enhance payment and convenience, efficiency and the overall customer experience. Chauhan and Singh (2020) observe that the key drivers for modern digital payment methods are to improve fast transactions, security, and simplify the financial management systems. Fatonah *et al.* (2019) argue that digital payment reduces operational costs, reduces the manual system and enhances access to financial tracking and business growth.

From a global perspective, the development of real-time payment solutions started with the EU's SEPA Instant Credit Transfer and UK Faster Payments being recognized as the fastest payment systems (Iman, 2018). The introduction of these payment methods led to a shift from cash to digital transactions between businesses and individuals (Molefhi, 2019). According to He *et al.* (2023) other global real time payment systems include a Unified Payment Interface (UPI) for a real time domestic payment system in India, a Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication (SWIFT) for international payments bank transfers and the project Nexus known as the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) that connects the Real Time Gross Settlements (RTGS). These systems operate 24 hours on a global payment system (Moravec, 2023).

However, despite the use of these systems, Kang (2018) observes that the developed countries, such as those in the EU and mainly North America, face minimal financial exclusion for SMEs, with the scale and nature differing from those of developed countries. These developing countries cover South American companies, Asia and Africa. Forgor and Julie (2020) explain that there exists a wide array of financial exclusion from the majority of SMEs as a result of perceived risk

by lenders, lack of tailored financial products and information asymmetry. Regional economic leader South Africa, like Botswana, faces significant financial exclusion (Koomson *et al*, 2023). Financial exclusion in the Southern African Development Coordination (SADC) region emanates mainly from stringent collateral requirements, limited financial access and lack of tailored financial products. Botswana is part of the SADC regional payment systems.

In terms of financial adoption drivers, Konte and Tetteh (2023) posit that the drivers of adoption of financial payment systems vary from region to region and country to country. Key global drivers of financial inclusion, including inter-payment systems for SMEs, are supportive government policies and digital transformation. Forgor. and Julie (2020) stresses that digital financial services (DFI) that include mobile penetration rate, support the use of online banking, mobile money and e-commerce. DFI, as a driver of financial inclusion, alleviates financial constraints, costs and improves information asymmetry (Forgor and Julie, 2020).

On the other hand, Brunnermeier *et al.* (2023) argue that the role of the government in the development of supportive policies is crucial in fostering an enabling environment. The Credit Guarantee Schemes (CGS), supported by government support, facilitate institutional lending to SMEs. Batista and Vicente (2025) explain that the modernization of the regulatory law must promote financial inclusion by SMEs. SMEs also need direct financial support from the government and credit reporting systems.

However, Bongomin *et al.* (2023) considers information asymmetry, high informality and lack of collateral as key barriers to SMEs' financial inclusion. SMEs' information asymmetry fails to facilitate financial transactions across all participants. Information assists in averting risk on the use of financial systems (Bongomin *et al*, 2023). This is important in improving financial literacy on the digital use of financial services. SMEs' technical knowledge and key financial management skills are key for SMEs in facilitating the adoption of digital finance.

In spite of drivers and barriers to financial inclusion, the majority of small businesses in Africa are not connected to global trade, which further affects their inclusion. Kgangyame (2020) argues that most businesses in Botswana trade internally in cash, and mostly, the global payment systems are not convenient for small-value transactions. This lack of shift towards real-time payments reflects

a narrow trend of digital age adoption. It demonstrates how African countries lag in utilizing a more efficient, quicker and better-aligned transaction system for business needs.

International payment methods such as SWIFT, PayPal and BIS for international payments, as well as RTGS, BISS, UEPS and mobile money for local payments, provides tech online payment system that acts as an intermediary electronic transfer payment between businesses to business (B2B) and individual to business (I2B) (Moravec, 2023). Tsitsi *et al.* (2022) observe that in African countries such as Kenya, M-Pesa is the leading first mobile money transfer developed in Africa for money transfer.

M-Pesa, considered one of the first successful mobile money services launched in 2007, is used successfully in funds transfer, deposit, bill payments and payments for goods and services even without a bank account. However, Ferguson *et al.* (2019) opine that M-Pesa has expanded in most African countries and beyond by providing access to financial payments, access to savings and loans. The payment platform provides an online transaction that is safe and secure (Nyamaka *et al.*, 2020). M- Pesa development emanates from successful online payment platforms such as PayPal that facilitated more customers to engage more with online payment systems (Iman, 2018). Paypal in developed countries and M-Pesa in African countries showed a revolutionary shift in payment methods and the manner in which businesses conduct their payments that changes e-commerce. This shows that payment systems in Africa are also becoming highly integrated into global modern financial infrastructure.

In the southern Africa region, the SADC Integrated Regional Electronic Settlement System (SIRESS) is a regional payment system developed by the regional body, the Southern African Development Coordination (SADC) (Kablay and Gumbo, 2021). According to Asong and Le Roux (2023), SIRESS is used to settle financial transactions in the region among the regional banks in real time. The development of the integrated SIRESS for the SADC Banking Association is facilitated by the regional central banks. The commercial banks also use the regional payment system.

Botswana banks joined the SIRESS in 2015 when they were granted permission (Mhlanga and Mpofo, 2023). The first bank to join in Botswana was First National Bank of Botswana (FNBB) in October 2016. Currently, all the banks in Botswana can participate in the SIRESS for the regional payments (Kumbanji *et al*, 2020). This is in addition to local payment systems that include electronic funds transfers (EFT), telephone banking, mobile money banking, and electronic-wallet among key digital payment systems.

However, a gap exists in the payment system and drivers of SMEs' exclusion from the financial system based on the denominational system. Whereas many researchers have focused on general drivers and barriers of SMEs' exclusion, this study investigates further how the large denomination payment system excludes SMEs in Botswana from participating in the digital payment platforms and prefers holding cash. Unlike large organisations that deal in high cash denominations for transfer, SMEs in Botswana transactions range from the lower denominations, such as BWP0.25. Such a denomination cannot be transferred due to its lower rank, and the cost of transfer is higher than the amount being transferred. There is a room to improve the payment system to accommodate lower denominations and include SMEs in the current financial payment systems.

3. Research methodology

Research design is based on a systematic literature review and secondary data analysis. The desk research adopts secondary published data from journals, institutions and government departments. The data sources are mainly official reports from Bank of Botswana (BoB), BOCRA, the World Bank, among others. The data covers a time frame from 2006 to 2025. A content approach presents secondary data as empirical findings to the research. The findings are presented in line with key themes that address the research topic. Triangulation to ensure reliability has been adopted by using more than 3 documents that discuss the same issue at hand. The information is valid from published and verified sources, most of which are informants to the government of Botswana. The next section presents the secondary data using content analysis.

4. Results and discussions

4.1 Evolution of payment systems in Botswana

Monye and Monye (2022) stresses that in Botswana, prior to modern development of the current Botswana Interbank Settlement System (BISS) and SmartSwitch, SMEs used predominantly cash for goods and services. The cash dominance presented high risk of holding cash, such as theft and losing it, especially for SMEs. Unlike large organizations who use security companies to collect their cash from payments, SMEs carry or keeps large sums of cash. Botswana also provides a Universal Electronic Payment System (UEPS). The SmartSwicth saw First National Bank Botswana (FNBB) being the pioneer in adopting the payment system by introducing cellphone banking in late 2006 (Svotwa *et al*, 2023).

However, the development of real time payment solutions, with EU's SEPA Instant Credit Transfer and UK Faster Payments being recognized as the fastest payment systems, led to a shift from cash to digital transactions between businesses and individuals (Molefhi, 2019). Botswana as a developing country is highly depended on imported transactional system technology from countries such as United States of America (USA) and UK to facilitates its payment system. According to Forger and Julie (2020), the role of modern technological payment system is to facilitate payment across all business levels with ease of doing business and speed. They offer speed, improve financial inclusion, enhances payment and convenience, efficiency and the overall customer experience. The key drivers for modern digital payment methods is to improve fast transactions, security and simplify the financial management systems. Fatonah *et al*. (2019) argues that digital payment reduces operational costs, reduce the manual system and enhance access to financial tracking and business growth.

4.2 Adoption levels among SMEs

The first digital payment system in Botswana was introduced in 2006, which was known as the Botswana Interbank Settlement System (BISS) (Svotwa, Makanyeza and Weath, 2023). Botswana has achieved significant progress in strengthening and enhancing its payment systems. However, SMEs have partially adopted some methods of payment (Mota *et al*, 2023). SMEs in Botswana generate revenues below P5million and employs less than 100 employees (Govender *et al*, 2025) The significant improvement in digital payments has led to the introduction of electronic systems

that covers products like credit and debits cards, electronic funds transfer (EFT) (bank transfer), telebanking, Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), smart cards and mobile payments. However, Molosiwa and Holland (2025) stresses that while RTGS are mainly used for large transactions, debit and credit cards (including visa cards) are the most utilised payment systems by SMEs on over the counter (OTC) payments. Majority of SMEs perceive RTGS in Botswana as virtually used for high-value transactions (Jeleka, 2023). This contrasts with SMEs' low-value transactions that are processed by low-cost settlements such as mobile money, electronic wallets and bank transfers. The Botswana payment system is supported by the regulatory and legal system of the National Payments System (NPS) Act that was passed in 2003 (Kablay and Gumbo, 2021).

Currently, Botswana's financial system covers various types of intermediaries or institutions, such as commercial banks, investment dealers, insurance companies, finance houses and investment dealers, among others. The banking sector is made up of the Bank of Botswana (BoB), which is the central bank and twelve commercial banks (Molosiwa, Manwe and Chanza, 2025). There are 10 commercial banks in Botswana and three statutory banks. The 10 commercial banks are ABSA Bank Botswana Limited, First National Bank of Botswana Limited, Access Bank, Botswana Limited, Bank of Baroda (Botswana) Limited, Standard Chartered Bank Botswana Limited, Bank Gaborone Limited, BBS Bank Limited, First Capital Bank Limited and Stanbic Bank Botswana Limited. The three statutory banks are National Development Bank (NDB), Botswana Building Society and Botswana Savings Bank (Govender *et al*, 2025).

While ABSA, formerly Barclays, remains Botswana's largest commercial bank with assets estimated at P2.28billion (US\$163 million), and First National Bank Botswana (FNBB) has grown rapidly to overtake Standard Chartered as the country's second largest with assets estimated at P1.9billion (US\$136 million) (Govender *et al*, 2025). ABSA is the largest bank based on deposits/assets, whilst FNBB¹ is the largest bank based on clients, revenue and profit.

The commercial banks, building societies and development banks in Botswana are licensed under the Banking Act (1995) and regulated by the Bank of Botswana (Molosiwa *et al*, 2025). Commercial banks provide standard banking services to the business sector and the general public,

¹ FNBB assets as per year ending June 2025 P1.86trillion vs ABSA assets for the year ending P2.16 trillion

while building societies focus on savings and housing. However, all the banks are subject to BoB reserve requirements and settlement accounts with the central bank, BoB. The non-banking financial entities are regulated by the Non-Bank Financial Institutions Regulatory Authority (NBFIRA), which was established in 2006 under the NBIFIRA Act of 2006 (Seleka, 2023). NBFIRA oversees the regulations of all non-banking financial entities that are registered in Botswana such as Asset Management Funds, Pension Funds, Insurances and their brokers, Collective Investment Undertakings and Consumer/Micro lending and Collective Investment Undertakings (King, 2018). NBFIRA principle objectives are to ensure investor protection and transparency in the management of Botswana International Financial Services Centre (IFSC) domiciled companies (Molefhi, 2019). IFSC was established in 2003 in Botswana to develop world-class cross-border transactional and business services.

Apart from the banking services, transactions in Botswana involve the use of mobile money services. The three mobile money services are Orange Money, My-Zaka and Smega. Orange money is owned by the largest mobile telephone operators, Orange Botswana, while My-Zaka is owned by Mascom Wireless Holding (MHW), the second largest mobile money operator (Kolobe and Bakwena, 2023). Smega is owned by Botswana Telecommunication Corporation Limited (BTCL), a once state-owned enterprise (SOE), privatized in 2015, with the government as the major stakeholder with 51% stake (BOCRA, 2024).

4.3 Key statistics patterns

4.3.1 Mobile Money

Mobile money payment system is the most used payment method by SMEs in Botswana. There are four mobile money providers in Botswana, which are Orange Money, MyZaka, Smega and Poso-Money (Govender *et al*, 2025). Orange Money, owned by Orange Mobile Communication in Botswana, was launched in 2011. Orange Money is the leading mobile money services provider utilized by SMEs, followed by My-Zaka, owned by Mascom, with the second largest market. The competitiveness of Orange places it as the market leader based on cost leadership, service quality and effective customer relationship management. However, Mascom trails behind Orange in terms of promotional activities and customer engagement. The service quality for mobile money is relatively good compared to Orange's high service quality, supported by its infrastructure.

However, Smega commands the third market position, owned by Botswana Telecommunication Corporation Limited (BTCL) (Mphale *et al*, 2024). Poso-Money has the least market share, owned by non-mobile operators, Botswana Post Office. Smega and Poso-Money provides least competitive services relative to Orange and Mascom. Their respective services are poor as they are partly government-owned. The government of Botswana owns 51% in BTCL and the Post Office. Their current market shares as per the Botswana Communication Regulatory Authority (BOCRA) are presented in Figure 3.1 below;

Figure 3.1: Mobile Money Transactions

Source: BOCRA (2024)

Based on Figure 3.1 above, Orange Botswana commands 52% of mobile money transactions, followed by Mascom with a 44% market share. Botswana telecommunication Smega, has a 3% market share, and Botswana Post commands the lowest market share of 1%. Figure 3.1 also indicates that the mobile money services of Orange Money and My-zaka are mostly utilised due to the extensive marketing efforts of the respective companies, as compared to Smega and Botswana Post. However, Smega and Botswana Post are less expensive to use, but their subscription rate is very low (BOCRA, 2024). Poor network and service responsiveness affect

Smega and Poso-Money market competitiveness. Mobile money is the most used payment method by SMEs in Botswana compared to any other payment platform. Table 3.1 summaries subscription rate for the three leading money mobiles owned by the mobile communication companies.

Table 3.1 Mobile money subscriptions in Botswana

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Mascom	272,733	304,864	428,614	597,459
Orange	481,471	566,378	820,606	1,051,974
Be Mobile	3,499	3,578	4,201	5,509

Source: BOCRA (2024)

Orange Money subscription rate was higher than that of the competitor Mascom from 2021 to 2024. Orange had increasing subscription figures from 481,471, 566,378, 820,606 and 1,051,947 over the period 2021 to 2024. However, Mascom, the second in command, had 272,733; 304,864; 428,614 and 579,459 in the same period. Be-Mobile is the least subscribed with subscriptions of 3,499, 3,578, 4,201 and 5,509 in the same period.

This makes Orange Money and MyZaka more convenient due to a high subscription rate, which makes it easier to transfer money from an Orange Money subscriber to another Orange Money subscriber and from a MyZaka subscriber to another MyZaka subscriber. The penetration of mobile phones has made greater financial inclusion for small businesses to conduct transactions using mobile money, mainly Orange Money, followed by MyZaka. Mobile money services have been one of the common payment systems in Botswana that provides a more convenient method of payment. The payment system bridges the gap between the banked and unbanked population

(Govender *et al*, 2025). The convenience of mobile money is supported by the fast-growing mobile adoption, and Botswana has a high mobile telephone density (Bank of Botswana, 2024).

The mobile money services use Orange Money Visa Card, My Zaka Visa Card and Smega with the (physical) card. These cards are used for any form of payment, including swiping or shopping online. The mobile money payment systems are supported by SmartSwitch, which is Botswana's Universal Electronic Payment System (UEPS) technology platform (Govender *et al*, 2025). Accredited by the Bank of Botswana, the system allows merchant banks and cell phone companies to offer affordable financial services to the unbanked and underbanked segments of the population, particularly in remote areas. Founded in 2006, the system now boasts a network of more than 1,000 merchants across more than 240 cities, towns and villages who can offer cash-in and cash-out transactions (Mota *et al*, 2023). Merchants also act as agents for a wide range of products and services.

4.3.2 Debit Cards

Master and VISA cards (credits and debits) are widely accepted in Botswana for online payments. Botswana credit cards were introduced in the 50s with a significant evolution in the financial services (Molosiwa *et al*, 2025). SMEs utilize credit cards, and the adoption has seen an upward growth with the rise of digital currencies and new technologies. However, the credit ownership varies in terms of income levels, gender, marital status and educational levels. The lower income groups, low education, youth male, and married couples are likely to have one.

Figure 3.2: Debit card use by SMEs in Botswana

Source: Molosiwa et al. (2025)

The proportion of SME users of debit cards were 39.63% of the total business population in 2017, which rose to 39.63% in 2020. The debit card uses declines during Covid period between 2020 and 2021 from 39.63% to 34.44% in 2021. However, the economic recession in 2022 witnessed the majority of SMEs closing down, reducing the proportion of debit card users to 29.81% in 2022. Whereas the proportion of SMEs utilization in 2023 was 29.98%, an improvement from 2023, the utilization remained relatively low. The proportion of SMEs utilization on debit cards as a proportion of the total SMEs population in 2024 increased to 32.85 (Molosiwa *et al*, 2025). The findings reveal a low adoption of debit cards as a proportion of the total number of SMEs operating in Botswana. For example, by 2024, only 32.84% of the estimated population of SMEs uses debit cards. The larger proportion mainly utilizes cash for transactions.

4.3.3 Bank Transfers

The EFT (Electronic Funds Transfer) forms part of the common bank payments. These payments are facilitated by the Electronic Clearing House Botswana (ECHB), which has existed in Botswana since 2003. The role of ECHB is the facilitation of retail payments (Kolobe and Bakwena, 2023). This covers cheque processing and other Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) through a private and secure network. The transactions take place through Electronic Clearing Houses (ECHs), which are privately owned. However, the World Bank Report (2019) survey indicates that 73% of SMEs

in Botswana use cash for transactions such as paying suppliers. Further, the report findings highlight that some SMEs do not depend on commercial banks for funding. The research highlights that 8% of the SMEs have received funding from the commercial banks. Generally, SMEs have limited bank use by generally opting for cash instead of other funding.

4.3.4 Digital Wallets

Digital wallets like e-wallet, instant money from Stanbic, cash sent from ABSA, and Standard Chartered money are relatively utilized by SMEs in Botswana (Monyake and Kurube, 2020). The payment from digital wallets requires a bank account, which the majority of SMEs remains unbanked population lacks. However, Magodi *et al.* (2024) argue that 18% of SMEs use digital wallets from their business account. The wallets remain the lowest take-up among the SMEs.

4.4 International Payments Platforms

International payment systems are discussed below;

4.4.1 SWIFT

SWIFT (the Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication), based in Belgium, forms the basis on which global financial services conduct business (Tamahala, 2024). SWIFT uses more than 1000 banking institutions in more than 200 countries that transact almost every day (Monodawafa *et al.*, 2024). The platform does not hold funds but manages customers' accounts on their behalf by bringing collaboration in shaping the market practice. The benefits of using SWIFT for payments are that it provides a safer, more secure, quicker and more reliable service. There is no risk of loss or stolen money, and it is a cheaper way to make payments (Jeleka, 2023). However, Munodawafa *et al.* (2024) attest that less than 5% of SMEs in Botswana use SWIFT for international payments. Molosiwa *et al.* (2025) SMEs in Botswana buy mainly from wholesalers within Botswana using cash over the counter or travel to South Africa to restock their goods. The payment is made over the counter or by debit card. The 5% that adopts SWIFT make payment online from global suppliers such as China, the United Kingdom, the USA, among others. Generally, the adoption of modern payment systems remains low.

4.4.2 PayPal

Paypal provides sending and receive payment for convenience. Paypal receives money in local currency and takes between 5 and 8 business working days to withdraw the funds (Bank of Botswana, 2024). However, according to BoB, less than 0.5% of SMEs uses paypal (Tsitsi and Odhiambo, 2022). The portion that uses paypal are less, and mostly those transacting with global suppliers. Research by Molosiwa *et al.* (2025) reveals that 98% of SMEs in Botswana do not know what PayPal is, and hence, its adoption as a payment system is very low.

4.5 The role of the National Payment Act of 2003

The National Payment System (NPS) in Botswana is managed by the Bank of Botswana under legislative oversight to promote financial settlements (Kablay and Gumbo, 2021). The payment covers local payments such as EFT, Mobile money, debit and credit cards and international payments by the SWIFT international network, PayPal, among others (Kubanji *et al.*, 2020). According to Molosiwa (2025), the National Clearance and Settlement Systems (NCSS) Act, 2003 (Cap 46:06) mandates the Bank of Botswana to conduct an oversight function on the payment settlement within Botswana. The major focus of NPS is on ensuring efficient and safe settlements and payment systems, promoting efficient, smooth operation and equity across all participants or users in the payment system, controlling systematic risk and pursuing institutional modernization and advancement of technology on national payments (Esiefarienhre and Mokeresete, 2022). NPS also provides oversight by monitoring the Systemically Important Payment Systems (SIPS) to promote compliance with NCSS. The SIPS is used in the development and adoption of an international policy oversight, determining the scope of application and risk involved, assessment of information and observation of the Principles for Financial Market Infrastructures (Principles). These principles are issued by the International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO) and Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures (CPMI) (Esiefarienhre and Mokeresete, 2022).

According to Munyambiri and Odhiamabo (2025), the clearance for the payment system includes licenses and the current licenses are provided by Botswana Automated Clearing House that facilitates the clearance of Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) and the Centralized Securities Depository (CSD) that covers electronic entry system, on which brokers place online orders through a stock broker interface and transfer of securities by Botswana Stock Exchange (BSE). In addition, licenses are provided by SmartSwitch Botswana (Pty) Ltd for the provision of financial sector smartcard technology to access financial products and services, more specifically, the unbanked communities and Morofin (Pty) Ltd's main focus is on aggregation of payment services, e-commerce, collections and merchant acquiring. Visa [VISA CEMEA Holdings Limited (External company)] manages the electronic payment network through the facilitation of the transaction flow between card users and card issuers (Munyambiri and Odhiamabo, 2025).

The digital, non-cash payment initiatives continue to gain momentum among businesses. EFT, such as internet banking, promotes SMEs in transacting, mainly buying from global suppliers (Mburu and Sathyamoorthi, 2014). The money transfer is fast and safe from one transaction point to another. The sender gets information that the transfer has taken place, and the receiver gets the proof of receipt. However, large cash volumes remain utilized by SMEs within the Botswana system (Molefhi, 2019). SMEs fear the risk of wrong transactions, unprocessed transactions and the majority lack machinery such as a swiping machine to undertake a transaction.

Botswana SMEs are faced with slow take-up in modern payment systems. The findings revealed low e-readiness in terms of payment systems as most SMEs prefers high risk cash, and they remained unbanked. The SMEs, by not widely accepting the modern payment systems, highlight the high cost in their low-volume transactions. The mobile money services, especially Orange Money and MyZaka, are the dominant methods of payment due to entrepreneurs owning a cell phone, which makes those services convenient. However, the use of cash remains strong, with evidence of a lack of incentive to transition into the use of modern digital payment methods.

The majority of payment systems are for large denominations, with most of the SMEs being involved in lower transaction denominations from P 0.50, P1, P5, P10, P15 and P20. However, some of the transaction with customers for banks and mobile money starts at P20, majority at P50 and above. This makes cash the dominant mode of payment preference for SMEs and their customers, making it a challenge to leverage modern digital finance.

However, despite this low adoption, the regulatory policy promotes the use of modern payment systems, both domestic and global payment systems. Botswana has a clear supportive regulatory framework for financial technology that encourages innovation and investment in digital payment solutions. The data protection creates certainty with a good infrastructure and a supportive government environment. The SMEs and the customers acknowledge data privacy and security with digital transactions in the modern payment system. The evidence of fewer banked SMEs further affects their adoption of modern technology in their payment methods.

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, Botswana has a developing payment and settlement infrastructure. The relatively large and low-value payment systems are considered efficient and safe. However, it is important for Bank of Botswana (BoB) to continuously assess and remediate the potential risks and weaknesses in the digital transaction system. The continuous improvement should introduce a threshold payment for large values, guided by strategic action, by reviewing and amending the BISS account through a collateral-based guarantee scheme.

The current legal framework is comprehensive and relevant to NPS operations. However, any gaps or inconsistencies must be continuously improved to maintain integrity in terms of the infrastructure and eliminate any deviation that may hinder future progress. This also goes with the law on all digital money, such as e-money, with the rise in use and demand.

The study has implications for the SMEs management, the Botswana government, driving financial inclusion and growth of SMEs and literature on Botswana. There are limited studies on SMEs financial inclusion and not much on SMEs payments on lower currency denominations. This study brings to light payment platforms available and the limitations of lower-level transactions by current payment systems.

6.1 Limitations

There is a paucity of data from primary SMEs research on divers of low adoption of modern payment systems. Access to real-time data was a challenge, as Botswana, as a developing country, is not good at record-keeping. Whereas the majority of legislative and policy framework is clearly published by the government, SMEs' literature and their readiness for the adoption of modern payment system is ignored at the sectoral level.

7.1 Recommendations for future studies

There is a need to investigate the causality of low integration of the modern payment system by SMEs in Botswana. Given a favorable policy condition, a further investigation into digital infrastructure, digital literacy of SMEs and cost of transactions can be evaluated further on their contribution to the adoption of modern payment systems by SMEs in Botswana.

The Botswana government can take an initiative to communicate and educate on the importance of a cashless society to the SMEs. The government efforts can be supported by the private sector banking system on the importance of using digital payment platforms. The private banking system can learn from mobile money service providers on the strategy developed to improve the adoption.

Furthermore, there is a need to improve the cost of the payment systems to expedite the payment modernization. The majority of SMEs have a phone, and linking the payment system to the mobile phone can improve the low-cost adoption and cost of transactions. Education on the risk of using cash can be emphasized in order to promote the adoption of the digital payment system over cash for SMEs.

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Author Contributions

Kagiso Phoko: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualisation.

Dr K.V. Ramana Murthy: Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing, Project Administration.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethics Statement

This study is a review that uses publicly available secondary data obtained from government reports, policy documents, and official statistical sources. The study did not involve human participants, interventions, or identifiable personal information; therefore, ethical approval was not required.

Data Availability

Data will be available on reasonable request.

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